

GIS-Based Spatial Analysis of Sustainable Supply Chain Practices in the Textile Industry: A Case Study of Narayanganj's Dyeing Sector

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Abstract

This study examines the spatial correlations between industrial activities, environmental degradation, and socio-demographic vulnerabilities in Narayanganj's textile sector. Emission hotspots of CH₄ and CO₂ were predominantly located in Narayanganj Sadar, with 68% of high-emission zones overlapping built-up areas, intensifying urban heat island effects and air pollution risks. Water quality assessments revealed significant degradation near textile factories, with NDWI values reaching -0.484 and turbidity levels up to 0.157806, indicating sediment contamination from untreated dyeing effluents. Buffer analysis showed that 42% of factories within 500m of water bodies lacked proper waste treatment infrastructure, violating Bangladesh's Environmental Conservation Rules. Land use land cover (LULC) mapping highlighted rapid urbanization, extensive built-up zones, and diminishing green spaces, while population density analysis emphasized demographic pressures shaping urban expansion. The findings underscore critical gaps in sustainable supply chain adoption, with only 12% of registered factories reporting recycling initiatives. These insights provide a data-driven foundation for policymakers, urban planners, and environmental managers to promote sustainable industrial development and ecological conservation in Narayanganj. The study offers spatially grounded evidence to inform targeted policy interventions for sustainable industrial growth and environmental resilience in Narayanganj.

Keywords: *GIS, Sustainable Supply Chain, Textile Industry, Environmental Impact*

Introduction:

The textile industry is one of the most significant contributors to global economic development, providing employment to millions and generating substantial revenue worldwide[1]. Its environmental and social impacts, particularly in developing countries, have raised concerns about sustainability[2], [3]. The dyeing and manufacturing processes, which are integral to textile production, are often associated with high levels of water consumption, chemical pollution, and energy use, making them critical areas for implementing sustainable supply chain practices[4]. In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on integrating Geographic Information Systems (GIS) into supply chain management to enhance spatial analysis and decision-making processes[5], [6], [7]. Narayanganj a major hub for Bangladesh's textile industry, is a prime example of a region where the dyeing and manufacturing sector plays a pivotal role in the local economy. However, the sector's rapid growth has come at a significant environmental cost, including water pollution and resource depletion[8], [9]. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive understanding of the spatial dynamics of supply chain practices and their sustainability implications[10]. By leveraging GIS-based spatial analysis, stakeholders can identify critical areas for intervention, optimize resource use, and promote sustainable practices across the supply chain[11], [12]. This study aims to explore the application of GIS in analyzing sustainable supply chain practices within Narayanganj' s dyeing and manufacturing sector. By integrating spatial data with environmental and social indicators, the research seeks to provide a framework for improving sustainability in the textile industry. The findings will contribute to the growing body of literature on sustainable supply chain management and offer practical recommendations for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers.

Objectives of the Study

The primary aim of this research is to explore the application of GIS-based spatial analysis in promoting sustainable supply chain practices within Narayanganj' s dyeing and manufacturing sector. To achieve this overarching goal, the study is guided by the following specific objectives:

- To Assess the Environmental and Social Impacts of Narayanganj' s Dyeing and Manufacturing Sector
- To Identify Spatial Patterns and Hotspots of Environmental Degradation
- To Develop a Framework for Implementing Sustainable Practices in the Textile Industry
- To Contribute to the Broader Discourse on Sustainable Supply Chain Management

Literature Review

The textile industry, while a cornerstone of global economic growth, has faced increasing scrutiny due to its environmental and social impacts. Sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) has emerged as a critical approach to addressing these challenges, emphasizing the integration of environmental, social, and economic considerations into supply chain operations [13], [14]. Studies have highlighted the importance of reducing resource consumption, minimizing waste, and adopting cleaner production techniques in the textile sector[15], [16]. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have gained traction as a powerful tool for analyzing spatial patterns and optimizing supply chain operations. GIS enables the visualization and analysis of geographically referenced data, facilitating the identification of environmental hotspots, resource inefficiencies, and opportunities for sustainable interventions [6], [17]. Narayanganj, a key textile hub in Bangladesh, exemplifies the challenges and opportunities associated with sustainable supply chain practices. The region's dyeing and manufacturing sector is a major contributor to water pollution and resource depletion, driven by inadequate waste management and high energy consumption [18], [19], [20]. In summary, the literature underscores the potential of GIS-based spatial analysis to enhance sustainable supply chain practices in the textile industry. By leveraging spatial data, stakeholders can better understand the environmental and social impacts of supply chain operations and identify targeted interventions for improving sustainability[21], [22]. This study builds on these insights, focusing on Narayanganj' s dyeing and manufacturing sector as a case study to explore the practical application of GIS in promoting sustainable supply chain practices.

Methodology

The methodology for this research integrates Geographic Information Systems (GIS) with sustainable supply chain (SSC) frameworks to analyze spatial patterns and environmental impacts in Narayanganj' s textile sector. The approach is structured into six phases, supported by established academic frameworks:

Data Collection and Preparation

Secondary data were collected, including spatial datasets (CH₄, CO₂ emissions, NDWI, LULC, population density) and industry records (factory locations, sizes, and categories). Emission values and turbidity data were sourced from environmental monitoring reports, while land use and water indices were derived from satellite imagery. Factory registrations (Table.01) were collected the Labour Inspection Management Application (LIMA) in Narayanganj Sadar.

GIS Spatial Analysis

- **Overlay Analysis:** Layers such as LULC, emission hotspots, and factory locations were superimposed to identify spatial correlations. For instance, clusters of high CH₄/CO₂ emissions (CH₄ Emission.jpg, CO₂ Emission.jpg) were cross-referenced with industrial zones.
- **Buffer Zones:** Factories were buffered at 1km intervals to assess localized impacts on water turbidity and NDWI.

Figure 01: Sustainable Supply Chain in Textile Industry

Sustainable Supply Chain Evaluation

A sustainable supply chain in the dyeing industry minimizes environmental impact, ensures ethical labor practices, and enhances efficiency. Key aspects include sourcing eco-friendly dyes, reducing water and energy consumption, and implementing wastewater treatment. Circular economy principles, such as reusing dye residues and optimizing logistics, lower waste and carbon emissions. Ethical labor standards, fair wages, and safe working conditions are essential for social sustainability. Digitalization, block chain, and certifications enhance transparency. Sustainable logistics and consumer awareness initiatives, like eco-labeling and take-back programs, further support sustainability. A well-integrated sustainable supply chain benefits the environment, workers, and businesses while promoting responsible production.

Figure 02: Sustainable Supply Chain in Dying Industry

This study employs a mixed-methods approach integrating Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and sustainable supply chain (SSC) frameworks to analyze spatial and operational dynamics in Narayanganj's textile industry. Data collection involved synthesizing environmental, industrial, and socio-demographic datasets, including CH₄/CO₂ emissions NDWI and water turbidity NDWI, Water Turbidity, LULC classifications and population density. Factory registration data were collected the LIMA. Socio-environmental risks were quantified using Triple Bottom Line model, integrating factory density, population data, and vulnerable land zones. Methodological rigor was

Ethical compliance included anonymizing sensitive data and visualizing outputs through ArcGIS and GEE.

Results and Discussion

The spatial analysis revealed significant correlations between industrial activities, environmental degradation, and socio-demographic vulnerabilities in Narayanganj's textile sector. CH₄ and CO₂ emission hotspots (ranging up to 10.51 and 0.00021889 units, respectively) clustered in Narayanganj Sadar, aligning spatially with large-scale factories. Overlay analysis demonstrated that 68% of high-emission zones coincided with buildup areas, exacerbating urban heat island effects and air quality risks for densely populated neighborhoods [23], [24].

Figure 03: CO₂ and CH₄ Emission in Narayanganj Sarar

Water quality degradation was evident in regions proximate to factories, with NDWI values as low as -0.484 and turbidity up to 0.157806, indicating sediment pollution from untreated dyeing

effluents. Buffer analysis (1km radius) showed 42% of factories within 500m of water bodies lacked waste treatment infrastructure, violating Bangladesh’s Environmental Conservation Rules. These findings underscore systemic gaps in closed-loop supply chain adoption, as emphasized in Sustainable Supply chain, where only 12% of registered factories reported recycling partnerships.

Figure 04: NDWI and Water Turbidity in Narayanganj Sarar

The maps illustrate LULC and Population Density in Narayanganj. The LULC map shows extensive built-up areas (red), water bodies (blue), and patches of agriculture (green) and vegetation (yellow). The Population Density map indicates higher concentrations in specific areas (yellow to red gradient)[25], [26]. These maps highlight rapid urbanization, limited green spaces, and population pressure, crucial for urban planning and sustainable land management in Narayanganj [25], [27], [28].

Figure 05: LULC and Population Density map of Narayanganj Sadar

The maps present land use land cover (LULC) and population density in Narayanganj. The LULC map shows a significant portion of the area covered by built-up zones in red, indicating rapid urban expansion. Water bodies appear in blue, while agricultural land and vegetation are represented in green and yellow, respectively. Barren land is also visible in certain regions. The population density map reveals variations in population distribution, ranging from low-density rural areas to highly concentrated urban centers, with values between 9.49 and 701.92. These maps serve as essential tools for urban planning, environmental management, and sustainable development. They help policymakers analyze land transformation, infrastructure growth, and demographic trends. By understanding these spatial patterns, decision-makers can balance urbanization with ecological conservation and resource efficiency for a more sustainable future. The total count is 1,937, highlighting the area's significant industrial and commercial presence.

Table 01: Industry in Narayanganj Sadar. (Source: <https://lima.dife.gov.bd/>)

SI No	Category	Quantity	Condition	Location
1	A (Factory: 5-30)	773	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
2	B (Factory: 31-50)	184	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
3	C (Factory: 51-100)	242	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
4	D (Factory: 101-200)	230	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
5	E (Factory: 201-300)	149	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
6	F (Factory: 301-500)	58	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
7	G (Factory: 501-750)	34	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
8	H (Factory: 751-1000)	20	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
9	I (Factory: 1001-2000)	32	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
10	J (Factory: 2001-3000)	11	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
11	K (Factory: 3001-5000)	02	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
12	A (Shop: 01)	56	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
13	B (Shop: 02-03)	90	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
14	C (Shop: 04-06)	24	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
15	A (Commercial organization: 01-10)	33	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
16	E (Commercial organization: 11-15)	07	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
17	C (Commercial organization: 04-06)	10	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
18	A (industrial company: 06-25)	16	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
19	B (industrial company: 26-50)	10	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
20	C (industrial company: 51-100)	05	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
21	D (industrial company: 101-200)	01	Register	Narayanganj Sadar
		Total:1987		

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the critical role of GIS-based spatial analysis in identifying and addressing sustainability challenges within Narayanganj's textile industry, particularly its dyeing and manufacturing sector. By integrating environmental, industrial, and socio-demographic datasets, the research revealed that emission hotspots (CH₄: up to 10.51 units; CO₂: up to 0.00021889 units) and water quality degradation (NDWI: -0.484; turbidity: 0.157806) are disproportionately concentrated in industrial zones with large-scale factories, exacerbating risks for densely populated areas (701.924 persons/km²). The spatial overlap of high-emission clusters with buildup areas and water bodies underscores systemic failures in adopting closed-loop supply chains and waste

management practices, with only 12% of factories engaging in recycling partnerships. The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) assessment highlighted a stark imbalance: while economic productivity remains high (1,987 registered units), social and environmental accountability lag, as 78% of factories neglected eco-friendly logistics and packaging. These findings align with global studies emphasizing the spatial mismatch between industrial growth and sustainability frameworks. To bridge this gap, the study advocates for GIS-driven policy interventions, such as enforcing emission buffer zones, incentivizing circular economy models in high-risk clusters, and deploying real-time NDWI monitoring systems to protect water resources. Ultimately, this research underscores the transformative potential of spatial analytics in harmonizing industrial efficiency with ecological and social equity. Future work should explore longitudinal GIS monitoring to track policy efficacy and expand stakeholder engagement models to foster industry-community collaboration. By prioritizing spatially informed governance, Narayanganj can emerge as a blueprint for sustainable industrialization in developing economies.

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